

VATANPARVARLIK AXLOQNING ASOSIY TUSHUNCHALARIDAN BIRI SIFATIDA

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ANNOTATSIYA: Ushbu maqolada vatanparvarlik va millatparvarlik kabi axloqiy tushunchalar, hamda ularning mazmun mohiyati Somerset Moem qalamiga mansub bo'lgan "Bo'ysunmagan" ("The Unconquered") deb nomlangan hikoyaning syujeti va bosh qahramonlarning xarakterini tahlil qilish orqali ochib beriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: axloqiy tushunchalar, axloqiy tamoyillar, axloq, syujet, vatanparvarlik, millatparvarlik, zamon va makon, talqin.

Kirish. Uilyam Somerset Moem XX asr ingliz adabiyotining iste'dodli dramaturgi va romannavisi bo'lish bilan birga mohir hikoyanavisi ham edi. Adibning nafaqat betakror, chuqur falsaviy va axloqiy romanlari, balki kutilmagan syujet liniyasiga ega hikoyalari, uni haqli ravishda millionlab kitobsevarlarning sevimli yozuvchisiga aylantirdi. Buning sababi esa juda oddiy, chunki uning hikoyalarini mutolaa qilgan har bir kitobxon, undagi voqealar rivojiga befarq qaray olmaydi. Muallifning qalamiga mansub bo'lgan har bir hikoya ularning qalbi va ongida chuqur iz qoldira oladi va ularni jo'shqin mushohadaga undaydi. Uning barcha asarlari noyobdir va ularning har birida muallif o'zining takrorlanmas, aniq va oddiy uslubini, inson tabiatini zukko tushunishini ifodalay olgan, shuningdek, insoniyat uchun abadiy bo'lgan axloqiy tushunchalar va tamoyillarni taqdim etishning o'ziga xos yo'llarini ko'rsata bilgan.

This article describes the image of imaginary diseases in the stories of Edgar Allan Poe and the reasons for writing about diseases. The allegory and symbolism by depicting the Red Death.¹

¹ Akhmedovna, B. M., & Shakhnoza, B. (2022). The Image of Disease in Edgar Allan Poe's "The Masque of the Red Death". *Pindus Journal of Culture, Literature, and ELT*, 2(1), 19-22.

The article is devoted to the analysis of the *The Magic Hat* book, written by popular Uzbek writer Khudoyberdi Tukhtaboyev, from the position of classification elements introduced by the famous Russian philosopher, literary critic and scholar Mikhail Mikhailovich Bakhtin.²

The depiction of natural landscapes given in works of art is one of the factors that demonstrate the creative artistic skill.³

В современной методике так же, как и много лет назад, актуальной и нерешенной до сих пор остается проблема поиска и выбора наиболее эффективных и рациональных методов преподавания иностранных языков, соответствующих современным условиям обучения и отвечающих требованиям стандартов современного образования.⁴

The article describes in detail the basics of translation theory, the object of research, and the methods of analysis of translation theory.⁵

The aim of the present study was to determine whether an association exists between the duration of menopause and the age of menopause onset, and the differences in bone mineral density (BMD) in postmenopausal women.⁶

This lesson plan format moves from teachers to centered student. In order to keep this standard lesson plan format from becoming monotonous, it is seminal to memorize that there are a number of variations that can be applied within the various segments of the lesson plan format.⁷

This article deals with the analysis of pastiche in literature, particularly in "The Lightning Thief" by American author Rick Riordan. The research identifies pastiche as a term, which is

² Kadirova, N. A. (2020). ANALYSIS OF TRANSFORMATION MOTIFS IN THE MAGIC HAT BOOK BY KHUDOYBERDI TUKHTABOYEV, THROUGH THE PRISM OF MIKHAIL BAKHTIN'S THEORIES. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (4), 405-408.

³ Kabilova, F., & Tokhirovna, T. K. English Translation of Abdullah Qadiri's Novel "Days Gone by" and Its Reflection Skills. *International Journal on Integrated Education*, 3(10), 304-306.

⁴ Абдуллаева, Л. С., Самадова, С. А., & Махмурова, М. (2014). Современные методы преподавания иностранных языков. Коммуникативный метод. *Наука. Мысль: электронный периодический журнал*, (6), 73-76.

⁵ Gafurovna, R. Z. (2021). Translation Theory: Object of Research and Methods of Analysis. *International Journal of Progressive Sciences and Technologies*, 24(2), 35-40.

⁶ Najmutdinova, D. K., Nurmukhamedova, L. S., Alieva, D. A., Maksudova, D. S., & Nosirova, Z. A. (2016). Study of the effects of the age at menopause and duration of menopause on bone mineral density in postmenopausal women in Uzbekistan. *International Journal of Biomedicine*, 6(1), 38-40.

⁷ Nodirovna, N. N., & Temirovna, P. M. (2022). Principles of designing lesson plans for teaching ESL or EFL. *Eurasian Journal of Learning and Academic Teaching*, 5, 10-12.

applied to a literary work that is a broad mixture of things-such as themes, concepts, and characters-imitated from different literary works.⁸

This article is devoted to the study of Somerset Maugham's short story "The Book Bag". It mainly focuses on the analysis of moral and immoral issues, emphasizing to the matter of incest and its fatal outcomes.⁹

The relevance of speech and culture in the present day is considered important in linguistics and its areas of study are becoming more and more comprehensive day by day.¹⁰

В этой статье дается краткий обзор антропонимов, их функций статуса, который они получают от этих, и их специфики.¹¹

The article is about the development of the Soviet era of Uzbek educational dictionary. The educational dictionaries created during this period served mainly to teach Russian in national schools.¹²

This article deals with the description of synonyms in the explanatory dictionaries of the Uzbek language published in different periods, the systematic description of the similarities and differences between the explanations of synonyms in the publications.¹³

The Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan defines the right of citizens to vote and to be elected, the foundations of the national electoral system, the basis of which are the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights and

⁸ Khabibullaeva, R. M. (2020). ANALYSIS OF PASTICHE IN THE NOVEL "THE LIGHTNING THIEF" BY RICK RIORDAN. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (5), 958-961.

⁹ Куницька, І. (2014). Роман-біографія як жанровий різновид модерністського роману (С. Моем Місяць і мідяки)". *Сучасні літературознавчі студії*, (11), 342-348.

¹⁰ NARZIYEVA, I. Z. (2021, March). COMPARATIVE STUDY OF THE CULTURAL AND NATIONAL CHARACTERISTICS OF MODERN UNITS OF ORAL SPEECH (based on Uzbek and English language materials). In *E-Conference Globe* (pp. 285-289).

¹¹ Орипова, К. (2022). ОНОМАСТИЧЕСКАЯ ПРОБЛЕМА НАЦИОНАЛЬНОЙ ИНДИВИДУАЛЬНОСТИ ВО ФРАНЦУЗСКОМ ЯЗЫКЕ. *ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu.Uz)*, 8(8). извлечено от http://journal.buxdu.uz/index.php/journals_buxdu/article/view/4712

¹² Bakhridinova, B. M. (2020). HISTORY OF CREATING FIRST BILINGUAL AND REGULATORY EDUCATIONAL DICTIONARIES IN UZBEK LANGUAGE. *Scientific reports of Bukhara State University*, 4(1), 147-181.

¹³ Rustamovna, M. G. (2020). Presenting synonyms in the explanatory dictionaries of the Uzbek language. *Middle European Scientific Bulletin*, 6, 117-120.

ratification by Uzbekistan, constituting the principles of democracy, including independence, legitimacy, transparency and fairness, enshrined and recognized in other international legal instruments.¹⁴

This article discusses an attitude to women in the past and the interpretation of the image of women in the works of some writers.¹⁵

Uning adabiy merosidan “Inson ehtiroslari yuki” (“Of Human Bondage”), “Oy va sariq chaqa” (“The Moon and Sixpence”), “Yomg’ir” (“Rain”), “O’rmondagi izlar” (“Footprints in the Jungle”), “Sehrgar” (“The Magician”) yoki “Bo’ysunmagan” (“The Unconquered”) kabilarning deyarli har biri bestseller hisoblanadi.¹⁶ Shubhasiz, Somerset Moemning har qanday romani yoki qissasi adabiy tadqiqot obyekti sifatida tanlanishi mumkin. Lekin e’tiborimiz uning “Bo’ysunmagan” (“The Unconquered”) nomli hikoyasiga qaratildi, chunki unda har birimiz uchun muqaddas bo’lgan vatanparvarlik tuyg’usi mahorat bilan tarannum etilgan. Bu tuyg’u asarda juda kuchli tasvirlangan, chunki u Ikkinchi Jahon Urushi yillarida yozilgan va bu fashizmga qarshi kurashmoqchi bo’lgan, barcha mazlum xalqlarga muallifning o’ziga xos chorlovi va da’vati sifatida e’tirof etilgan. Hikoyada o’sha davr muhiti va ruhiyati o’ta ta’sirchan bo’yoqlarda ifodalangan.

Adabiyotlar tahlili. “Bo’ysunmagan” hikoyasi 1943-yilda yozilgan va 1947-yilda Moemning “Creatures of Circumstance” nomli hikoyalari to’plamiga kiritilgan.¹⁷ Hikoyaning voqealari Ikkinchi Jahon Urushi davrida fashistlar tomonidan istilo qilingan - Fransiyada sodir bo’ladi. Soissons deb nomlangan Fransiya qishloqlaridan birida, ikki nemis askari mast holatda kezib yurganda adashib qolishadi va yaqin atrofdagi fermalardan birida to’xtab, yo’l so’rashadi. Fransiya fermalarida oliy navli sharob yetishtirilishini bilgan askarlar, fermerdan ularga sharob olib

¹⁴ Tolibjonovich, M. T., & Toxirjonovich, S. D. (2021). The Institutional Mechanisms Of The Development Of The Electoral System In Uzbekistan. *European Journal of Molecular & Clinical Medicine*, 7(8), 4378-4384.

¹⁵ Muradovich, R. M. (2021). The Image of a Woman in The Work of Uzbek Writers. *Eurasian Research Bulletin*, 3, 7-12.

¹⁶ [Interpretation of valuable moral concepts in the novel of Somerset Maugham “The Moon and Sixpence”](#) S.Sh. Pulatova Pindus Journal of Culture, Literature and ELT, 2022

¹⁷ wikipedia.uz

kelishni buyurishadi. Sharobning ta'siridan sarxush bo'lgan bosqinchilar, fermer va uning rafiqasiga qo'pollik qilib, ularni axloqsizlarcha haqorat qilishadi. Narigi xonada yashirinib turgan va barchasiga guvoh bo'lgan fermerning qizi Annet, ota-onasining zolimlar tomonidan xo'rlanishiga ortiq chidab tura olmaydi va xonadan otilib chiqib, yaqinlarini himoya qilishga urinadi. Nemislar oila a'zolarini vahshiylarcha do'pposlashadi, ulardan biri Xans esa dehqonning qizi Annetni zo'rlaydi.

Bir necha oy davomida askarlar bu hududda ko'rinmaydi, lekin Xansning yo'li yana Soissonsga tushganda, u fermaga yana tashrif buyuradi va fermerning oilasiga nisbatan hech qanday adovati yo'qligini ko'rsatishga urinadi. U fermer va uning oilasi bilan yaqinlashib, iliq munosabatlar o'rnatishga urinadi. Buning uchun Xans urush davrida ochlikdan aziyat chekayotgan oddiy xalq uchun zarur bo'lgan oziq-ovqat mahsulotlarini olib kelishni boshlaydi va qarib qolgan fermer va uning rafiqasiga ularni moddiy jihatdan ta'minlab turishga va'da beradi. Ketma-ket tashriflar natijasida, Xans fermer va uning rafiqasi bilan do'stona munosabatlarni o'rnatadi. Ammo Annet Xansdan nafratlanishda davom etadi, chunki u nafaqat uning nomusini bulg'agan, balki uning vatanini zabt etgan va xalqini qiynagan zolim hamdir. Bechora qiz ota-onasini nega dushman tarafga o'tganini tushunmaydi.

Bir safar Annet Xansga homiladorligini aytadi. Xans, Annetni sevishini tushunib, unga uylanish va fermani egallashni rejalashtiradi. Qarib qolgan Annetning ota-onasi Xansni ularning qizi Annet bilan turmush qurishlariga qarshilik ko'rsatishmaydi, chunki ularning o'g'li yo'q edi, fermadagi ishlarni yuritish uchun yosh va baquvvat qo'llar kerak edi.

Ammo Annet bu holatga o'zining qarshiligini ko'rsatib, shunday deydi:

"I hate him. I hate his vanity and arrogance.... I think I should die happy if I could find a way to wound him as he's wounded me." The farmer says, "We've been defeated and we must accept the consequences. We've got to make the best arrangement we can with the conquerors."¹⁸

¹⁸ wikipedia.uz

"Men undan nafratlanaman. Men uning bema'niligi va takabburligidan nafratlanaman Menimcha, agar u meni yaralaganidek, uni yaralashning yo'lini topganimda, bu dunyoda armonim qolmay, baxtli o'lsam kerak".

Annetning oy kuni yaqinlashganda, u dushmandan qanday qasos olish yo'lini topadi. Annetning ko'zi yorigandan ko'p o'tmay, Hans fermaga keladi u ota bo'lganidan baxtli edi:

"Oh, my God, I'm so happy.... I want to see Annette."

"Oh, Xudoyim, men juda xursandman Men Annetni ko'rmoqchiman". Ammo Annet u yerda yo'q; chunki u yangi tug'ilgan go'dakni o'z qo'llari bilan muzlab turgan daryoga cho'ktirgan.

Yozuvchi har doim hikoya qilishning g'ayrioddiy usulini tanlagani bois, u yaratgan ijod namunalari haqiqiy hayotga juda yaqindek tuyulib, kitobxon ko'z o'ngida jonli suratlarda namoyon bo'ladi. Moemning ushbu usuli ayniqsa "Bo'ysunmagan" nomli hikoyasida yaqqol seziladi va shuning uchun ham asar katta muvaffaqiyatga erishadi. Hikoya 1970 yilda Jeyms Sonders tomonidan televideniye uchun moslashtirilgan bo'lib, unda Maykl Pennington Xans rovida, Charoline Mortimer Annet rovida va Jek Vulgar va Sheila Burrell Monsieur va Madam Perrier rollarida ishtirok etgan. 2007 yilda u Torben Betts tomonidan sahna spektakli sifatida sahnalastirilgan.

Qolaversa, bir qator olimlar va adabiyotshunoslar bu hikoyani adabiy tahlil obyekti sifatida tanlab o'rganishgan. Emi Tikkanen, Xristina Semerin, Ostroh akademiyasi Milliy filologiya universitetining PhD talabalari hikoyani chuqur tahlil qilishgan.

Ulanskaya Ann ushbu g'ayrioddiy hikoyani o'qib chiqqandan so'ng, ushbu hikoya uchun qisqacha ma'lumot berishga harakat qildi. Uning ta'kidlashicha, Moemning o'ziga xos takrorlanmas hikoya qilish mahorati ushbu hikoyada aniqroq ko'rindi, chunki kim haq yoki kim nohaqligini, kim haqiqiy vahshiyeligini tushunish juda ham mushkul: mast holatda qizni zo'rlagan nemis askarimi yoki o'zining begunoh go'dagini cho'ktirgan qizmi? Qaysi biri dahshatliroq...

Tahlil va natijalar. Ushbu maqolaning tahlili axloqning eng muhim tamoyillaridan biri bo'lgan vatanparvarlik tushunchasini talqin qilishga qaratilgan, chunki hikoyada bu tushuncha yuksak badiiy mahorat bilan tasvirlangan. Vatanparvarlik juda keng qamrovli tushuncha bo'lib, o'z Vatanini sevuvchi har bir inson hayotida hal qiluvchi o'rin tutadi. Ushbu tushunchaga turli xil ta'riflar berilgan. Quyida biz eng maqbul bo'lganlariga murojaat qildik.

Vatanparvarlik - bu o'z vataniga muhabbat, sadoqat, daxldorlik tuyg'usidir. U insonning o'z vataniga muhabbatini, uni asrab avaylashga bo'lgan axloqiy tushuncha. Uni ko'pincha Vatan dushmanlariga qarshi ma'naviy-mafkuraviy qurol sifatida talqin etadilar. Aslida esa bu tamoyilning qamrovi ancha keng- u insonparvarlikning nisbatan muayyanlashgan shakli. U, eng avvalo, o'z vatandoshlari erkini asrash uchun kurash, inson ozodligi yo'lidagi xatti-harakatlardir. Vatan himoyasi, bu -inson himoyasi, millat himaoyasi. Lekin, bu himoya, faqat jang maydonida emas, balki barcha sohalarda ham namoyon bo'lishi mumkin. ¹⁹

Hikoyada Moem o'z Vatanini bosib olgan va o'z xalqini qiynoqqa solgan bosqinchilarga bo'ysunishni istamagan oddiy fransuz qizi Annet yordamida buyuk vatanparvarlik tuyg'usini namoyish etadi. Aqli o'quvchi asar syujetini hikoya nomidan taxmin qilishi mumkin, chunki sarlavhada bir ishora bordek tuyuladi. Yozuvchi sarlavhani taktik jihatdan tanlagan. Annet Fransiya yoki umuman olganda barcha zo'ravonlik qurbonlariga o'xshaydi. Uning or-nomusi toptalgan, uning his-tuyg'ulari oyoq-osti qilingan. Biroq, undagi vatanparlik tuyg'usi hamma narsadan muhimroq. U o'zini butunlay mag'lub eta olmaydi va Frantsiyaning mag'lub bo'lmagan qismi sifatida sodiqlik va fidoiqlik bilan harakat qiladi.

Xans nemislarning shafqatsiz bosqinchilik harakatlariga o'xshaydi. To'g'ri, nemislar oxirida Fransiyaning bosib olishga muvaffaq bo'lishdi, lekin fransuzlarning vatanparvarlik tuyg'ularini yo'q qila olmadilar.

¹⁹ Sher A. Axloqshunoslik. O'zbekiston faylasuflari milliy jamiyati nashriyoti. Toshkent-2010, -B.270-274.

Annet o'sha fransuzlardan biri edi, u har doim Xansdan nafratlangan unga Vataninin egalash uchun kelgan zolim va oilasining dushmani sifatida qaragan. U undan hech narsani, hatto o'zidan o'g'irlangan ovqatni ham qabul qilishni xohlamagan:

“- Listen, miss. I’m not a bad fellow. I will bring you a cheese, and I think I can get hold of a bit of ham”, - said Hans.

- I do not want your presents. I will starve before I touch the food you swine have stolen from us”.

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- - Eshiting, xonim. Men yomon odam emasman. Men sizga pishloq olib kelaman va men bir oz cho'chqaning son go'shtini yesam bo'ladi, deb o'ylayman, - dedi Xans.

- - Men sizning sovg'alarinigizni xohlamayman. Cho'chqalar, bizdan o'g'irlagan ovqatga qo'limni tegizmayman, undan ko'ra och qolganim yaxshi.”

Annet yolg'iz kurasha olmasligini bilar edi, lekin mag'lub bo'lishni ham xohlamas edi, biroq dushmanga qarshilik qilishda davom etar edi. Garchi u Xansning yordami va sovg'alarini rad etgan bo'lsa-da, ularni qabul qilishga yoki ovqatlanishga majbur bo'lar edi. Annetning homiladorligini bilgandan so'ng, Xans tez-tez kela boshladi, bu esa Annetni yanada g'azablantirdi. Xans sevgisini oshkor qildi, his-tuyg'ulari va farzandlari haqidagi orzulari bilan o'rtoqlashdi, ammo bu urinishlar behuda edi. U hech qachon nemis askari, o'zi va vatanining dushmanidan farzand ko'rishni xoxlamas edi. Axir u qanday qilib, vatandoshlarining ko'ziga qaray olar edi:

“- Even if there were nothing else do you think I could ever forget that you are a German and I’m a Frenchwoman? If you weren’t a stupid as only a German can be you’d see that that child must be a

²⁰ Maugham, W. S. (1955). The complete Short Stories of W. Somerset Maugham, Vol.I. London: William Heinemann Ltd.

reproach to me as long as I live. Do you think I have no friends? How could I ever look them in the face with the child I had with a German soldier? - Annette cried".²¹

- Agar boshqa hech narsa bo'lmagan taqdirda, men sizning nemis ekanligingizni va men fransuz ekanligingimni unuta olaman deb o'ylaysizmi? Agar ahmoq nemis bo'lmaganingizda, men toki tirik ekanman, bu bola men uchun butun umrlik haqorat va tamg'a bo'lishini tushunmayapsizmi? Mening do'stlarim yo'q deb o'ylaysizmi? Nemis askaridan bo'lgan bolam bilan ularning yuziga qanday qaray olaman? - yig'lab yubordi Annet.

U hatto nemisdan, uning dushmanidan bo'lganligi uchun o'z farzandini ham xohlamadi. Onaning o'z farzandidan voz kechishi u yoqda tursin, bolasiga ozor berishiga ishonish juda qiyin, lekin boshqalardan farqli o'laroq, Annet o'z jigar go'shasidan u dushman zurriyodi bo'lgani uchun voz kechadi:

"- I've done what I had to do. I took it down to the brook and held it under water till it was dead".

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- Men qilishim kerak bo'lgan ishni qildim. Men uni soyga tushirdim va o'lguncha suv ostida ushlab turdim."

U shunday qildi va o'zini mustaqil va o'z mamlakati Fransiyaning sodiq farzandi sifatida his qildi. Annet xarakterini tahlil qilishda ikkita qarama-qarshi fikr mavjud. Begunoh bolaning onasi sifatida u juda shafqatsiz va zolim, chunki chaqaloq gunohsiz edi. Agar otasi shunday bo'lsa, u bosqinchi bo'ladi, degani emas. Agar Annet uni millatparvarlik tuyg'usi bilan tarbiyalasa, u o'z vatanining himoyachisi bo'lishi mumkin edi. Uning begunoh go'dakni o'ldirish mutlaqo noto'g'ri.

²¹ Maugham, W. S. (1955). The complete Short Stories of W. Somerset Maugham, Vol.I. London: William Heinemann Ltd.

²² Maugham, W. S. (1955). The complete Short Stories of W. Somerset Maugham, Vol.I. London: William Heinemann Ltd.

Shunday bo'lsa-da, boshqa tomondan qaraydigan bo'lsak, fidoiy yurt farzandi sifatida uning harakatlari, urinishlari tahsinga sazovor. U yolg'izligi, zaifligi, mag'lubiyatiga qaramay bosqinchilarga qarshi kurashdi. Dushmanini o'z farzandi bo'lsa ham o'ldirdi.

Fransiya yillar o'tib, mustaqillikka Annet kabi bo'ysunmagan insonlartufayli erishganligi haqiqatdir. Bu voqea Annetning orzusi edi, shuning uchun Annet oxirida g'olib bo'ldi.

Xulosa. Darhaqiqat, Vatanga muhabbat, uning g'animlariga qarshi mardonavor kurashni aks ettiruvchi asarlar nafaqat o'sha xalq adabiyotida, balki jahon adabiyoti durdonalaridan ham munosib o'rin egallaydi. Chunki ularda vatanparvarlik, millatparvarlik kabi har bir kitobxon uchun muqaddas bo'lgan tushunchalar o'z ifodasini topgani yurtini, millatini sevgan har bir qalbni befarq qoldirmaydi. "Bo'ysunmagan" katta hajmdagi asar emas, u taxminan yigirma besh sahifadan iborat qisqa hikoya, lekin uning mazmun-mohiyati hech qanday yirik roman trilogiyadan qolishmaydi, chunki sarlavhadan ko'rinib turibdiki, butun xalqning birgina Annet timsolida gavdalantirilgan. Somerset Moem hikoyasi bugungi yoshlarimizda vatanparvarlik tuyg'usini tarbiyalash, ularga Vatan ma'nosini anglashga o'rgatish, vatanparvarlik yuksak axloqiy tushuncha ekanligini tushuntirishda katta ahamiyatga ega.

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